

IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON COMPETITIVE PERFORMANCE OF MICRO, SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES

Richa Sethi & Ashish Chhimpa

Suresh Gyan Vihar University,
Malviya Nagar, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Abstract

Globalization refers to the increasingly global relationships of culture, people and economic activity. Most often, it refers to economics: the global distribution of the production of goods and services, through reduction of barriers to international trade such as tariffs, export fees, and import quotas. Globalization in India is generally taken to mean 'integrating' the economy of the country with the world economy. The real thrust to the globalization process was provided by the new economic policy introduced by the Government of India in July 1991. Globalization has led to an 'Unequal Competition' - a competition between 'giant MNC's and dwarf Indian enterprises'. The small scale sector is a vital constituent of overall industrial sector of the country. The small scale sector forms a dominant part of Indian industry and contributing to a significant proportion of production, exports and employment. Therefore, the present study analyzes the impact of globalization on competitive performance of Indian Small Scale Industries. The main theme of the paper is to evaluate the competitive performance of SSI, before and after liberalization and compare them with average annual growth rates, to know the impact of Globalization on the competitive performance of SSI. The period of the study is 1973- 2010 and based on secondary information .

Keywords:- Globalization, Small Scale Industries, Competitive Performance , Production, No. of Units, Export and Employment.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization signifies a process of internationalization plus liberalization, in which the world has become a small village due to the concept of globalization. The competition has become intense in every field. Nations fight with game plan to sustain their economy, by introducing new policies and announcing incentives to support mainly their economic- indicators. After the world economy was open to attack, the Indian economy has initiate to concentrate on the

development of small industrial base, which had contribute positively to the India's GDP; India's GDP growth is better than other developing countries with the developed small industrial sector.

In order to impart more vitality and growth to small scale sector, a separate policy statement has been announced for small, tiny and village enterprises on 6th August, 1991. This policy statement was a leap-forward because it was the first time that Government had issued a separate policy statement for the small and decentralized sector. This policy statement proposed some path- breaking measures to mitigate the handicaps that were faced up by small enterprises in respect. Government of India introduced a large number of innovative promotional measures to uplift the growth of small scale sector. Major features of the Small Industrial policy of 1991 were :

1. Emphasis to shift from cheap credit to adequate credit.
2. Equity participation by other undertakings (both domestic and foreign) up to 24 Percent .
3. Introducing of factoring services by banks.
4. Marketing of mass consumption goods under common brand name.
5. Setting up of sub- contracting exchanges.

6. Establishment of technology development cell.
7. Opening of quality counselling and technology information centres.
8. New technology up gradation programmes.

GLOBALIZATION

For the purpose of the argument in this paper, as well as understanding some of the responses to globalization, it is important to define what is meant by globalization. This is all the more crucial because even if we leave out the unambiguous supporters of globalization in its present form- those who hold that it is purely beneficial, and the benefits will 'trickle down' automatically to the poor- there are still widely differing conceptions of this process. Those who either oppose globalization, or are anxious about its potentially detrimental effects on employment and poverty, encompass a wide political spectrum. The extreme right oppose it from the standpoint of economic and cultural nationalism, and liberals might deplore the loss of national sovereignty because it reduces the effectiveness of state intervention to regulate capital and labour, alleviate poverty and so forth.

Globalization is the process of integrating various economies of the world without creating any hindrances in the free flow of goods and services, technology, capital and even labour or human capital. The term globalization has, therefore, four parameters:

1. Reduction of trade barriers to permit free flow of goods and services among nation-states; 2. Creation of environment in which free flow of capital can take place among nation-stated; 3. Creation of environment, permitting free flow of technology; and
4. Last, but not the least, from the point of view of developing countries, creation of environment in which free movement of labour can take place in different countries of the world.

Performance of MSMEs Sector in India – An Overview:

The MSMEs Sector continues to be a vibrant sector of the Indian economy. It is estimated that there are about 12.8 million units (over 90 per cent of total industrial units) in this sector employing nearly 31 million people. This sector contributes nearly 39 per cent of the total industrial production and accounts for approximately 33 per cent of the total exports. This sector has consistently registered a higher growth rate than the rest of the industrial sector. There are over 6500 products ranging from traditional to high-tech items, which are being manufactured by the small enterprises in India. After agriculture, the MSMEs sector provides the maximum opportunities for both self-employment and jobs in the country. The small enterprises sector in India holds great potential for further expansion and growth in the future. In fact, the employment potential of the sector is un-matched by any other sector of the economy. Economic development of a country is directly related to the level of industrial growth. The expansion of industrial sector leads to a greater utilization of natural resources, production of goods and services, creation of employment opportunities and improvement in the general standard of living. Small scale industries play a key role in our planned development with its advantages of low Investment, high potential for employment generation, diversification of the industrial base and dispersal of industries to rural and semi urban areas. The small-scale industries sector has been appropriately give a strategic position in our planned economy towards the fulfilment of the socio economic objectives particularly in achieving equitable growth.

The definition of small scale sector is broadened from small-scale industries to small scale enterprises that include all business enterprises in the services sector which provide service to industrial sector in addition to small scale industries taking into account all these factors, at present, Reserve Bank of India uses an expanded definition of small scale industries which include:(i) Small scale industrial undertaking which are engaged in the manufacturing, processing and preservation of goods in which the investment in plant and machinery not to exceed Rs. 5crore and Service enterprises Rs. 2crore. (ii) Micro enterprises whose investment in plant and machinery do not exceed Rs.25 lacs and service enterprise is Rs. 10 lacs. (iii) Medium enterprises' manufacturing division is Rs.10crore and its service division is Rs. 5 crore.

The development of small scale industries is being given due importance by the Government in order to achieve the following objectives:-

1. To provide additional employment opportunities.
2. To mobilise resources of capital and skill from various parts of the country.

3. To provide a more equitable distribution of national income.
4. To provide a helping hand to large industries and facilitate them in their work.

Challenges of Globalisation & Liberalisation for MSMEs in India:

1. With the liberalisation and globalisation of the Indian economy, the small enterprises in India have unprecedented opportunities on the one hand, and face serious challenges, on the other. While access to global market has offered a host of business opportunities in the form of new target markets, possibilities to exploit technological advantage, etc., the challenges in this process have flowed mainly from their scale of operation, technological obsolescence, inability to access institutional credit and intense competition in marketing.

2. The Government of India is fully aware of the challenges of globalisation and has taken appropriate measures for preparing the Micro & Small Enterprises (MSEs) to meet the challenges of liberalisation and globalisation. Taking a view of the whole situation, the Government has put in place several measures to help small enterprises to become globally competitive. These include schemes /programmes for technology upgradation, development of clusters of such industries, making collateral free bank credit available upto US\$ 1,25,000, creating awareness among these industries regarding export-related issues, etc. The Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSME) in India also conducting workshops on various aspects of WTO, Anti-dumping seminars, IPR, etc. to sensitize the MSEs entrepreneurs and other stakeholders about the likely impact of liberalisation and globalisation.

3. The Micro Small and Medium Enterprises Development (MSMED) Act, 2006 has been formulated as a response to the long-standing demand of the MSEs sector, the emergent need to provide a legal framework to address the developmental concerns of what is globally known as “small and medium enterprises”. The Act, inter-alia, provides the first-ever legal framework to facilitate the promotion and development of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSME), which comprises both manufacturing and services entities. It defines ‘medium enterprises’ for the first time and seeks to integrate the three tiers of these enterprises, namely, micro, small and medium. Establishment of specific Funds for the promotion, development and enhancing competitiveness of these enterprises, notification of schemes/ programmes for this purpose, progressive credit policies and practice, more effective mechanism for mitigating the problems of delayed payments to MSEs, etc. are some of the other features of this Act. The Ministry of MSME has also taken a view, in the light of liberalized provisions of the MSMED Act, 2006 to do away with the restrictive 24 per cent ceiling prescribed for equity holdings by industrial undertakings, whether domestic or foreign, in the erstwhile Small Scale Industries (now SMEs). This coupled with an expected legislation on Limited Liability Partnership (introduced in the Parliament by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs) is expected to pave the way for greater corporatisation of the Small & Medium Enterprises- thereby enhancing their access to equity and other funds from the markets of these products in keeping with the global standard.

NEED AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Small Scale Industry in India has been confronted with an increasingly competitive environment due to: (i) liberalisation of the investment regime in the 1990s, favouring foreign direct investment at the international level, particularly in socialistic and developing countries; (ii) the formation of the World Trade Organisations (WTO) in 1995, forcing its member- countries (including India) to drastically scale down quantitative and non quantitative restrictions on imports, and (iii) domestic economic reforms. The cumulative impact of all these developments is a remarkable transformation of the economic environment in which small industry operates, implying that the sector has no option but to ‘compete’. To compete in the international market, the Indian Government Announced a separate Industrial Policy for Small, Tiny and Village Industries on 6th August, 1991 and started some development programmes for the development of Small scale Sector. The main objective of the present study is to analyze the impact of globalization on the performance of small scale industries.

DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY

In the present study an attempt has been made to analyze the impact of globalization on the performance of small scale industries. For this, the growth pattern and some aspects of productivity in SSI sector in India have been

R. Sethi & A. Chhimpa / Impact of Globalization on Competitive Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

calculated. The study has been conducted with reference to the data related to the performance of Small Scale Industries in India. The SSI sector has been studied with the belief that they hold the largest share of Industrial Sector in India. The reference period for the analysis of the data has been taken from 1973-74 to 2009-10. The study period has been divided into two parts: pre liberalisation (1973-74 to 1989-90) and post liberalisation (1990-91 to 2009-10) to know the impact of globalization after liberalisation. For this, a comparative analysis of Average Annual Growth Rates for pre and post globalization periods has been carried out for key growth and performance parameters like number of units, production, employment and exports. The study has been based on secondary information. The data for the study purpose has been taken mainly from 'Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, Government of India' published by Reserve Bank of India in Handbook of Statistics on Indian Economy.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

All the indicators related to the growth of small scale industries has been computed from 1973 to 2010, in this 1973- 74 to 1989-90 (17 years) are taken under pre- globalization period and 1990-91 to 2009-2010 (20 years) are comes under post- globalization period. Means 17 – 20 years of performance of pre and post globalization has been compared. In this study there is only one limitation that in the case of exports data for the year 2008-2009 and 2009-2010 are not available.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Various studies have been conducted from time to time in different states of India on different aspects of small-scale industries. The most of the studies are related to financial aspect, growth of small scale industries, entrepreneurship in SSIs, WTO regime and small scale industries and also related to small industry and globalization. A review of imported studies is presented below:

Mathew, M.C. (2004) highlighted the reason for panic in all India census report on smallscale industries. The study observed that the vibrancy and dynamical of the sector anticipated under an era of deregulation and de-reservation remaining largely unrealized. The study stated that the country needs a strong small and medium enterprises policy, which was closely linked to its international commitments. The study suggested that at the strategy level, there were need to be mechanism by which the demography of small and medium enterprises sector itself becomes a matter of public security. Rajyalakshmi, N. (2004) reviewed the productivity awareness among SSI units in Visakhapatnam district of Andhra Pradesh at micro level and explored small- scale entrepreneurs, how they measured productivity in their units. The study based on primary data collected by using structured schedule through personal interviews. A sample of 200 SSI units has been selected for the study. The study found that Chemical units were more capital intensive and it was low in food and agro units. Productivity awareness was not noticed in the SSI units. The study concluded that Success in small industry will be best achieved if the productivity culture will be clearly understood by all the employees. Subrahmanyabala, M.H. (2004) highlighted the impact of globalization and domestic reforms on small-scale industries sector. The study stated that small industry had suffered in terms of growth of units, employment, output and exports. Researcher highlighted that the policy changes had also thrown open new opportunities and markets for the small-scale industries sector. The author suggested that the focus must be turned to technology development and strengthening of financial infrastructure in order to make Indian small industry internationally competitive and contribute to national income and employment. Sudan, F. K. (2005) described the challenges in Micro and Small Scale Enterprises Development and policy issues by arising different questions related to Micro and Small Enterprises. The study explained the meaning, advantages, problems and policy options of MSE sector. The study concluded that all the policies which were opted by GOI were the efforts to form a dynamic MSE sector and a diversified economy providing expanded employment opportunities to absorb all new labour force and offer exciting career opportunities.

Rathod, C. B. (2007) described the importance of small scale industrial sector and also the contribution of Indian small scale entrepreneurs in world economy. The main objective of the study was to study the growth and pattern of the SSI sector and identify the reasons for success/ failures, to evaluate the impact of globalization on SSIs and export opportunity, to identify the barriers and constraints that SSIs were facing to cope with globalization. The study analysed that SSI sector in India has been exhibiting a striking export performance; export had grown up to double digit from the last ten years. The study concluded that both opportunities and challenges were raised as the impact of globalization on Indian Industry as a whole and the small scale sector in particular. The study found that a major portion of our exports would have to gear up to the new era of boundary less economy. The study has

suggested that there was need for simplified legal and regulatory framework, good governance, sufficient and accessible finance, suitable infrastructure and competitive environment.

GROWTH OF SMALL SCALE INDUSTRIES IN INDIA: PRE AND POST GLOBALIZATION

The small scale industries play a significant role in boosting the overall economic growth of an economy. The small scale industries set- up by the entrepreneurs in different states and Union Territories of India have contributed to the increased shares in overall production, fixed investment, exports, Employment and capacity Utilization of SSI Units, etc. The importance of MSME sector in providing large scale employment is of paramount importance.

The policy framework right from the first plan has highlighted the need for the development of SSI sector keeping in view its strategic importance in the overall economic development of

India. The impact of Industrial liberalisation and deregulatory policies on the growth of small scale industries has been captured by computing and subsequently comparing the growth rates between pre and post globalization period. In this section, the overall performance of MSME sector has been examined in depth on the basis of the different parameters such as number of units, production, employment and exports.

NUMBER OF SSI UNITS

The working number of units in small scale sector in Pre and Post Globalization Period in India is show in the following table:

Table No. 1

(Units = Million Nos.)

Year	Units	% Increase to prev. year	Year	Units	% Increase to prev. Year
1973-74	0.42	-	1990-1991	6.79	273.08
1974-75	0.50	19.05	1991-1992	7.06	3.98
1975-76	0.55	10	1992-1993	7.35	4.11
1976-77	0.59	7.27	1993-1994	7.65	4.08
1977-78	0.67	13.56	1994-1995	7.96	4.05
1978-79	0.73	8.96	1995-1996	8.28	4.02
1979-80	0.81	10.96	1996-1997	8.62	4.11
1980-81	0.87	7.41	1997-1998	8.97	4.06
1981-82	0.96	10.34	1998-1999	9.34	4.12
1982-83	1.06	10.42	1999-2000	9.72	4.07
1983-84	1.16	9.43	2000-2001	10.11	4.01
1984-85	1.24	6.90	2001-2002	10.52	4.06
1985-86	1.35	8.87	2002-2003	10.95	4.09
1986-87	1.46	8.15	2003-2004	11.40	4.11
1987-88	1.58	8.22	2004-2005	11.86	4.04
1988-89	1.71	8.23	2005-2006	12.34	4.05
1989-90	1.82	6.43	2006-2007	26.1	111.48
-			2007-2008	27.27	4.51
-			2008-2009	28.51	4.53
-			2009-2010	29.80	4.53
AAGR	9.36		AAGR	4.14	

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, GOI.

AAGR= Annual Average Growth Rate or Exponential Growth Rate.

The data for the period upto 2005-2006 is of SSI, subsequent to 2005-2006 data with reference to MSME are being compiled.

R. Sethi & A. Chhimpa / Impact of Globalization on Competitive Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

Analysis: It is cleared from the above table that the Annual Average Growth Rate of number of units in the pre-liberalisation period, from 1973-74 to 1989-90 was 9.36 percent and in post-liberalisation it was 4.14 percent. In pre-liberalised period, the yearly growth rate was higher than average growth rate in the initial years and from 1984-85 to 1989-90; the yearly growth rate was less than average growth rate. In 1989-90, the yearly growth rate was least in the pre-liberalisation period. In the post-liberalisation period, in 1990-91 it was very high, in 2006-07 it was 111.48 and after that it was fluctuating between 3.98 percent and 4.53 percent. Most of the time, the yearly growth rate was less than average growth rate. The numbers of units were increasing in the study period but the average and yearly growth rate was higher in pre-liberalised period than post liberalised period.

PRODUCTION

Table no. 2 provides the information about the growth of Small Scale Sector on production front during the period of 1973-74 to 2010.

Table No. 2 (Production= Crores)

Year	Production (current prices)	% Increase to prev. Year	Year	Production (current prices)	% Increase to prev. Year
1973-74	7200	-	1990-91	78802	-40.44
1974-75	9200	27.78	1991-92	80615	2.30
1975-76	11000	19.57	1992-93	84413	4.71
1976-77	12400	12.73	1993-94	98796	17.04
1977-78	14300	15.32	1994-95	122154	23.64
1978-79	15800	10.49	1995-96	147712	20.92
1979-80	21600	36.71	1996-97	167805	13.60
1980-81	28100	30.09	1997-98	187217	11.57
1981-82	32600	16.01	1998-99	210454	12.41
1982-83	35000	7.36	1999-00	233760	11.07
1983-84	41600	18.86	2000-01	261297	11.78
1984-85	50500	21.39	2001-02	282270	8.03
1985-86	61200	21.19	2002-03	314850	11.54
1986-87	72300	18.14	2003-04	364547	15.78
1987-88	87300	20.75	2004-05	429796	17.90
1988-89	106400	21.88	2005-06	497842	15.83
1989-90	132300	24.34	2006-07	585112	17.53
			2007-08	790759	11.47
			2008-09	880805	11.39
			2009-10	982919	11.59
AAGR	19.45		AAGR	13.16	

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, GOI.

AAGR= Annual Average Growth Rate or Exponential Growth Rate.

Since 2001-02, Production figures are at 2001-02 prices.

Analysis: It is cleared from the above table that the Annual Average Growth Rate of production in the pre-liberalisation period, from 1973-74 to 1989-90 was 19.45 percent and in post-liberalisation it was 13.16 percent. In pre-liberalised period, the yearly growth rate was decreasing in the initial years from 1973-74 to 1978-79; the yearly growth rate was fluctuating from 1980-81 to 1983-84, after that it was shown increasing trend except in 1986-87. In the post-liberalisation period, in 1990-91 the yearly growth rate was very low, it was negative and

after that it was showed increasing trend from 1991-92 to 1994-95. The yearly growth rate was showing decreasing trend from 1995-96 to 2002-03 except in 1998-99 and 2001-02. Most of the time, the yearly growth rate was less than average growth rate. The production was increasing in the study period but the average and yearly growth rate was higher in pre- liberalised period than post liberalised period.

EMPLOYMENT

In India, the major argument for promoting small scale sector is that the small enterprises provide avenues for gainful employment. The performance of small scale sector in creating employment opportunities is really a matter of great interest. The following table provides the information of small scale sector on the growth of employment:

Table No. 3

(Employment= Million Nos.)

Year	Employment	% Increase to prev. Year	Year	Employment	% Increase to prev. Year
1973-74	3.97	-	1990-91	15.83	32.36
1974-75	4.04	1.76	1991-92	16.60	4.86
1975-76	4.59	13.61	1992-93	17.48	5.30
1976-77	4.98	8.50	1993-94	18.26	4.46
1977-78	5.40	8.43	1994-95	19.14	4.82
1978-79	6.38	18.15	1995-96	19.79	3.40
1979-80	6.70	5.02	1996-97	20.59	4.04
1980-81	7.10	5.97	1997-98	21.32	3.55
1981-82	7.50	5.63	1998-99	22.06	3.47
1982-83	7.90	5.33	1999-00	22.91	3.85
1983-84	8.42	6.58	2000-01	24.09	5.15
1984-85	9.00	6.89	2001-02	25.23	4.73
1985-86	9.60	6.67	2002-03	26.37	4.52
1986-87	10.14	5.63	2003-04	27.53	4.40
1987-88	10.70	5.52	2004-05	28.76	4.47
1988-89	11.30	5.61	2005-06	29.99	4.28
1989-90	11.96	5.84	2006-07	59.46	42.49
			2007-08	62.63	5.34
			2008-09	65.93	5.35
			2009-10	69.53	5.47
AAGR	7.25		AAGR	4.52	

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, GOI.

AAGR= Annual Average Growth Rate or Exponential Growth Rate.

Analysis: It is cleared from the above table that the Annual Average Growth Rate of employment in the pre-liberalisation period, from 1973-74 to 1989-90 was 7.25 percent and in post- liberalisation it was 4.52 percent. In pre- liberalised period, the yearly growth rate was more than average growth rate in the initial years i.e. from 1973-74 to 1978-79; after that

R. Sethi & A. Chhimpa / Impact of Globalization on Competitive Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

the yearly growth rate was too much decreased from 1979-80 to 1989-90, it was fluctuate between 5.02 percent and 6.89 percent. In the post- liberalisation period, in 1990-91 the yearly growth rate was very high than average growth rate. After that the yearly growth rate was fluctuated from 1991-92 to 2005-06. In 2006-07 the yearly growth rate was very high, thereafter it started showing a increasing trend. Most of the time, the yearly growth rate was less than average growth rate. The employment was increasing during the study period but the average and yearly growth rate as higher in pre- liberalised period than post liberalised period.

EXPORTS

In the context of liberalization and globalization of Indian economy, the performance of small scale sector in the field of exports needs a closer look as it is the strong performance parameter. The exports from small scale sector found to be higher from the total export. The exports of small scale sector are:

Table No. 4

(Exports= Million Nos.)

Year	Exports	% Increase to prev. year	Year	Exports	% Increase to prev. Year
1973-74	400	-	1990-1991	9664	27.16
1974-75	500	25.00	1991-1992	13883	43.66
1975-76	500	0	1992-1993	17784	28.10
1976-77	800	60.00	1993-1994	25307	42.30
1977-78	800	0	1994-1995	29068	14.86
1978-79	1100	37.50	1995-1996	36470	25.46
1979-80	1200	9.09	1996-1997	39248	7.62
1980-81	1600	33.33	1997-1998	44442	13.23
1981-82	2100	31.25	1998-1999	48979	10.21
1982-83	2000	-4.76	1999-2000	54200	10.66
1983-84	2200	10.00	2000-2001	69797	28.78
1984-85	2500	13.64	2001-2002	71244	2.07
1985-86	2800	12.00	2002-2003	86013	20.73
1986-87	3600	28.57	2003-2004	97644	13.52
1987-88	4400	22.22	2004-2005	124417	27.42
1988-89	5500	25.00	2005-2006	150242	20.76
1989-90	7600	38.18	2006-2007	182538	21.50
			2007-2008	202017	10.67
			2008-2009	NA	
			2009-2010	NA	
AAGR	18.66		AAGR	17.67	

Source: Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, GOI.

AAGR= Annual Average Growth Rate or Exponential Growth Rate.

Analysis: It is cleared from the above table that the Annual Average Growth Rate of exports in the pre-liberalisation period, from 1973-74 to 1989-90 was 18.66 percent and in post liberalisation it was 17.67 percent. In pre- liberalised period, the yearly growth rate was too much fluctuating; it was sometimes very high than average growth rate. In 1976-77, the yearly growth rate was 60 percent, it was highest during the pre- liberalisation. 1978-79 to 1984-85 the AAGR was yearly increasing or decreasing, in 1982-83 it was on the lowest peak

and showed negative trend. After this from 1985-86 to 1989-90, the yearly growth rate was increasing and reached at 38.18 percent. In the post- liberalisation period, from 1990-91 the yearly growth rate has changed its trend yearly, in one year its trend was increasing and than next subsequent year the trend was decreasing. It was least in 2001-02 and highest in 1991- 92. The exports were increasing during the study period but the average and yearly growth rate was higher in pre- liberalised period than post liberalised period.

CONCLUSION AND FINDINGS

MSMEs has performed extremely well and enabled our country to attain wide ranging events of industrial amplification and diversification. By its less capital investment and high labour combination nature, MSME sector has made important contribution to employment generation and also to rural industrialization. Globalisation has been affecting every economic activity in almost every country and Indian MSMEs are no exception. The performance of MSMEs ha a determining significance for Indian economic growth due to their substantial share of enterprises, employment, production and gross value added in industrial sector. However in general, Indian MSME lack technological strength to access and exploit the benefits emerging from the intensifying process of globalisation. Therefore, technological transformation of MSMEs should attract the focus of attention of policymakers. MSMEs should be enabled to achieve self-sustainable competitiveness and reap the fruits of globalisation for their own growth and the growth of the Indian economy.

In this study, an attempt has been made to analyze the impact of globalization on the performance of small scale industries. The comparative analysis of growth pattern of key parameters between Pre- and Post – Globalization periods reveals that the “globalization” had a negative impact on the growth of small scale sector measured in terms of number of units, production, employment and exports. A fall in the rate of growth of number of units and employment generation in post liberalisation period is a matter of serious concern for the policy- makers and planners. The result showed that globalization is almost a complete failure on growth front. To conclude, we can say that the recent trend of growth of MSME sector showed the trust of Indian economy on globalization and liberalisation, which has failed to render a positive impact on the growth of Indian Small Scale Sector. No indicator shows the positive impact, in each case the average growth rate is less in post- globalization period than pre- globalization period. The main findings of the study are:

1. In 1990-91, the growth of number of units is too much increased. It is increase from 6.43 to 273.08 percent. The units are increased from 1.82 million to 6.79 millions in numbers. In 2006-07 also units have increased to 111.48 percent, because of MSMED Act 2006 formed by Government.
2. The growth rate of production is decreased at a high rate in 1990-91; it showed the negative trend of growth and reached at -40.44 percent growth rate of production. Because of open market outer country sold their product easily in our country at lesser prices which reduced the demand of country products and so production had also affected, decreasing production drastically.
3. In the very first year of globalization the growth rate of employment has been increased which showed that after globalization employment opportunities were increased due to open market and liberalisation of establishing units in India by the outsiders which generate employment for our country. In 2006-07 also, the growth was high, which was 42.49.
4. The value of exports has increased after the globalization which means Indian MSME sector concentrates more on selling their products out of the country to earn more and more foreign currency. The growth rate of exports is highest in 1991-92 due to subsequent changes in Indian economy.

Overall, the impact of globalization on the performance of small scale sector is negative which a serious matter for planners.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bala, N, (20007), *Economic Reforms and Growth of Small Scale Industries*, Deep & Deep Publications, New Delhi.
- Bansal, S. K. (1992), *Financial Problems of Small Scale Industries*, Anmol Publications, New Delhi.
- Datt, R. And Sundaram, K. P. M. (1999), *Indian Economy*, 39th Edition, S. Chand & Company, New Delhi.
- Dr. Rajeev Kansal & Sonia (2009), "Globalisation and its impact on Small scale industries in India" *PCMA Journal of Business* Vol.1, No. (June,2009)pp. 135-146.
- Government of India (1971), *Small Scale Industries: A Guide and Reference Hand Book*, Nabhi Publications, New Delhi.
- Krishna, M. J. (2004), "World Trade Organisation and Its Implications on Small Scale Industries in Karnataka", *SEDME*, Vol. 31, No. 2, June 2004, PP: 91- 102.
- Mathew, M.(2004), " Small Industry and Globalization", *Economic and Political Weekly*, Vol. XXXIX, No. 20, 15 May 2004, Pg: 1999-2000.
- Nag, B. (2000), "WTO Regime and Its Implications for Indian Small and Medium Enterprises Sector", *SEDME*, Vol. 27, No. 3, September 2000, PP: 1- 17.
- Nallabala Kalyan kumar & Gugloth sardar(2011), "Competitive Performance of MSME in India", *Asia Pacific Journal of social sciences* Vol.III(1),Jan-June2011,pp128-146.
- Raghurama, A. (2004), "Small Scale Industries in Kerala- Competitiveness and Challenges Under Globalization", *SEDME*, Vol. 31, No. 2, June 2004, PP: 7- 17.
- Rajyalakshmi, N. (2004), "Productivity Awareness Among SSI Units: A Case Study", *The Indian Journal of Commerce*, Vol. 57, No. 2, April- June 2004, PP: 64- 72.
- Rathod, C. B. (2007), "Contribution of Indian Small Scale Entrepreneurs to Economic Growth in India: Opportunities and Challenges in Global Economy", *Prabandh- Journal of Management & Research*, Vol. 23, June 2007, PP: 1- 12.
- Subrahmanya, M.H. (2004), "Small Industry and Globalization: Implications, Performance and Prospects", *Economic and Political Weekly*, Vol. XXXIX, No. 18, 1 May 2004, Pg:1826-1834.
- Sudan, F. K. (2005), "Challenges in Micro and Small Scale Enterprises Development: Some Policy Issues", *Synergy: I. T. S. Journal of IT and Management*, Vol. 3, No. 2, July 2005, PP: 67-81.
- Varadarajan, D. B. (2008), "Kyoto Protocol,s Clean Development Mechanism- It's Feasibility to Indian Small Scale Industries Under Globalization", *Political Economy Journal of India*, Vol: 17, No. 1, January- June 2008, PP: 36- 44.
- www.rbi.org.in
- www.msme.in
- www.smallindustries.com